

DEVELOPMENT OF PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Annotation: *The article discusses the philosophical and social consciousness, the formation of philosophy as a science, the philosophical views of Central Asian thinkers.*

Keywords: *philosophy, consciousness, contemplation, man, state.*

The development of philosophy has a long history and is a special form of philosophical and social consciousness. Philosophy is the oldest and most interesting of human knowledge. Philosophy is the most ancient science, and its emergence dates back to the era of ancient slavery. Sources indicate that philosophy as a science was originally formed and developed in India, China, Greece, and Central Asian countries. Philosophy, its subject, the object of study, the problems of philosophy are issues that have long been of interest to scientists. Initially, philosophy encompassed not only the knowledge gained from people's life observations, but also their own thoughts about the universe. Thoughts on the subject of philosophy have changed over time, and philosophical understanding of the world has been expressed in various forms. First, the development of spiritual culture has had its influence on philosophy. Initially, the concept of philosophy was a symbol of "science" and was used in the broadest sense of "science". In ancient Greece, an attempt was made to define the subject of philosophy. The classification of sciences is an example of this. The subject of philosophical debate has been covered by medieval thinkers in Central Asia.

Abu Nasir al-Farabi said, "Philosophy is the essence of being; perfect and complete about the content of all that exists; the science that imparts knowledge. If the knowledge of existence is acquired, if it is taught about it, if the essence of the thing is known, if the meaning of the thing is understood, if there is a kind of belief and imagination in the brain on the basis of reliable evidence and documents, we call this knowledge philosophy ...", has created many works on philosophical problems. These are "The Word of Substance" ("The Word of the Word"), "The Book of Laws"

("The Book of the Doom Navomis"), and "The Word of the Meaning of the Concept of Philosophy." (Kamal doil means the name as-philosophy), The Book on the Necessity of Philosophy, The Origin and Classification of Sciences (Ija-al-umum).

Continuing the thought of Abu Ali Ibn Sina al-Farabi, the task of philosophy is to examine all existing things, the order of their origin, their interrelationships, the transition from one to another. Abu Ali Ibn Sina's philosophical views such as the Kitab al-Shifa, the Encyclopaedia, the Law of Medical Sciences, as well as the Risala al-Tayir (The Science of Kunt), Salomat wa Ipsal, and Hayit Ibn Yaqsan. found expression in his art pockets. Abu Abdullah al-Khwarizmi believes that philosophy consists of two parts, theoretical and practical. According to him, theoretical philosophy includes the natural sciences, theology, ie metaphysics and logic. In general, in the Middle Ages, the view that philosophy was a science of science was prevalent. One of the objects of study of philosophy and the most important is man. Man, his nature, attitude to the world, language, ethics, forms of manifestation of human abilities have fascinated philosophers. Socrates (ancient Greek philosopher) emphasized that philosophy is the understanding of life. A number of treatises by Aristotle, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Farabi, Beruni, and Descartes are devoted to the philosophical understanding of man. These include Abu Ali ibn Sina's On the Sciences and Hegel's Philosophy of the World. In general, the scope of philosophical problems includes the world, its structure, nature, society, man, man's place in society, man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Does it have boundaries?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them. Socrates (ancient Greek philosopher) emphasized that philosophy is the understanding of life. A number of treatises by Aristotle, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Farabi, Beruni, and Descartes are devoted to the philosophical understanding of man. These include Abu Ali ibn Sina's On the Sciences and Hegel's Philosophy of the World. In general, the scope of philosophical problems includes the world, its structure, nature, society, man, man's place in society, man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Does it have boundaries?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them. Socrates (ancient Greek philosopher) emphasized that philosophy is the understanding of life. A number of treatises by Aristotle, Abu Ali ibn Sina,

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In conclusion, it can be said that the formation and development of philosophy, the philosophical worldview, is connected with the development of society, social life. The historical roots of the revival of philosophy as a science go back to ancient times. Philosophy is of great importance in the correct understanding of the world and reality. The human worldview is first of all reflected in his spiritual world, in the culture of thinking, of the correct understanding of vocabulary.

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